

On the Study of the Indirect Application of Radioactive Nuclei in Analytical Chemistry. Part III

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Application of co-ordination compounds to extend the use of I^{131} , an easily available isotope of convenient half life, in the determination of mercury and cadmium has been made. The principle employed is to add excess of labelled iodine as KI to neutral solution of mercury or cadmium to which is then added a solution of copper ethylenediamine sulphate in slight excess. The precipitate is then allowed to settle and activity of a portion of the solution is measured with a liquid counter. The loss in activity is a measure of mercury or cadmium, as the case may be. Cadmium and mercury from 50 mg. to 0.1 mg. have thus far been estimated. The data lie always within statistical fluctuations. It can be claimed to be a very quick and reliable method for the estimation of mercury and cadmium even in such a very small concentration as mentioned above.

Use of radioactive nuclei in analytical chemistry has been discussed in some details in previous communications¹. Practice of using I^{131} in day-to-day analysis in a radio-chemical laboratory is very useful because of the convenient half life of the isotope in question and due to its easy availability in carrier-free state. Attempts have therefore been made to use co-ordination compounds of suitable nature to simplify chemical analysis with I^{131} as a measuring indicator. It was as early as 1929 Spacu and his co-workers² observed that complex ion like HgI_4^{2-} , CdI_4^{2-} etc. can be utilised for analytical purpose by its combination with another complex cation like $[Cu(en)_2]^{2+}$. The method, though claimed to be very rapid, had many drawbacks as regards solubility and stability of the compound at a convenient temperature.

The object of the present investigation is to simplify the procedure adopted by the previous workers² and to extend the principle to lower ranges of concentrations which are very convenient with I^{131} as a measuring indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carrier-free I^{131} was supplied by Messrs. Philips Roxane and all other reagents, viz., $(Cu SO_4, 5H_2O)$, $(3Cd SO_4, 8H_2O)$, and KI, used in the investigation, were of AnalaR quality. $[Cu(en)_2]SO_4$ in solution was prepared by mixing copper sulphate and ethylenediamine, the latter being slightly higher than the amount required for stoichiometric composition. Dilute sulphuric acid was dropped on the solution, thus prepared, till it was acidic to litmus. Mercuric chloride ($HgCl_2$) and cadmium sulphate ($3 Cd SO_4, 8H_2O$) were taken as primary standards for the preparation of stock solutions. The procedure adopted by us was to take a known amount of mercury or cadmium from the solution, mix it with a

1. Purkayastha and Verneker, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 487; 1962, 39, 180.
2. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 240, 334; 1932, 89, 187.

solution containing four times or even ten times the theoretical amount of potassium iodide (KI) as demanded by the composition MI_4^{2-} (where M stands for cadmium or mercury) and then to add some carrier-free I^{131} . The solution was warmed on a water bath and boiling copper ethylenediamine sulphate $[Cu(en)_2]SO_4$ solution was then added. The whole system was then brought to room temperature and the volume was made to the mark. A portion of the solution was pipetted and the amount of activity left in the solution was measured by a G. M. counter meant for measuring liquid samples. In order to avoid any solid matter entering the pipette, a piece of filter paper was wrapped on its tip. From the loss of activity, quantity of mercury and cadmium, as the case may be, was computed. The results obtained are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Estimation of cadmium as $Cu(en)_2CdI_4$ with I^{131} as indicator.

Cd. taken.	Iodine added.	$Cu(en)_2SO_4$ in terms of Cu.	Final volume.	Cd found.	% Error.
50.400 mg.	1064.40 mg.	120.0 mg.	25 ml	50.010 mg.	- 0.8
29.610	365.40	106.7	50	29.400	- 0.6
25.200	532.20	60.0	25	25.180	- 0.1
14.810	182.70	53.4	50	14.600	- 1.4
14.810	182.70	53.4	50	14.550	- 1.7
5.922	76.90	26.0	5	6.043	+ 2.0
5.922	76.90	26.0	5	6.088	+ 2.7
2.961	38.45	20.0	5	2.982	+ 0.6
2.961	38.45	20.0	5	2.964	+ 0.1
1.481	19.23	13.0	5	1.496	+ 1.0
1.481	19.23	13.0	5	1.460	- 1.4
0.740	28.85	26.0	5	0.745	+ 0.7
0.740	28.85	26.0	5	0.735	- 0.6
0.504	21.30	12.0	5	0.509	+ 1.0
0.504	21.30	12.0	5	0.502	- 0.3
0.252	10.65	6.0	5	0.261	- 0.4
0.252	10.65	6.0	5	0.252	$\pm$ 0.0
0.126	5.33	3.0	2.5	0.127	+ 0.8
0.126	5.33	3.0	2.5	0.127	+ 0.8
0.063	2.66	1.5	2.5	0.0584	- 9.0
0.063	2.66	1.5	2.5	0.0575	- 10.0

DISCUSSION

Although Spacu *et al.*² predicted that microdetermination with this reagent in case of mercury was possible, no body as yet tried to apply it because of the handicap mentioned in the literature; in the case of cadmium, he rather recommended to prepare the reagent^{2,3}

[Cu(en)₂](NO₃)₂. By the use of radioactive iodine it has been found by us that difficulties faced by them as regards washing the precipitate and drying in a special way can easily be avoided. Our method is not only simple for general use, but it also extends the range from macro to micro determination.

TABLE II

Estimation of mercury as Cu(en)₂HgI₄ with I¹³¹ as indicator.

Hg taken.	Iodine as led.	Cu(en) ₂ SO ₄ in terms of Cu.	Final volume.	Hg found.	%Error.
187.8000 mg.	2187.00 mg.	1309.00 mg.	50.0 ml	187.200 mg.	-0.30
62.6000	769.00	386.60	50.0	62.610	+0.02
62.6000	769.00	386.60	50.0	62.180	-0.80
62.6000	769.00	386.60	50.0	62.900	+0.50
62.6000	769.00	386.60	50.0	62.100	-0.80
31.3000	385.40	95.00	50.0	31.920	+2.00
31.3000	384.50	106.35	50.0	31.000	-1.00
31.3000	384.50	106.35	50.0	30.800	-1.70
15.6500	192.30	98.18	15.0	15.580	-0.40
15.6500	192.30	98.18	15.0	15.720	+0.40
15.6500	182.70	57.00	50.0	15.720	+0.40
9.3900	115.35	39.27	15.0	9.320	-0.80
9.3900	121.80	38.00	10.0	9.410	+0.20
6.2600	76.90	38.00	50.0	6.186	-1.30
6.2600	76.90	38.00	25.0	6.233	-0.50
3.1300	38.45	13.09	5.0	3.148	+0.60
3.1300	38.45	13.09	5.0	3.153	+0.60
3.1300	38.45	13.09	5.0	3.137	+0.30
1.5600	19.22	6.54	5.0	1.570	+0.70
1.5600	19.22	6.54	5.0	1.580	±0.0
0.7850	10.65	6.00	2.5	0.780	-0.70
0.7850	10.65	6.00	2.5	0.7850	±0.0
0.3925	5.33	3.00	2.5	0.3903	-0.60
0.3925	5.33	3.00	2.5	0.3967	+1.10
0.1963	2.665	1.50	2.5	0.1978	+0.80
0.1963	2.665	1.50	2.5	0.1954	-0.50
0.1570	2.130	1.00	2.5	0.1561	-0.05
0.1570	2.130	1.00	2.5	0.1568	-0.15
0.0785	1.065	0.50	2.5	0.0773	-1.20
0.0785	1.065	0.50	2.5	0.0776	-1.20
0.03925	0.639	0.40	2.5	0.0374	-5.00
0.03925	0.639	0.40	2.5	0.0368	-6.00

We have not yet been able to find out a carrier which can selectively co-precipitate [Cu(en)₂]MI₄ (where M stands for Cd or Hg) leaving excess of iodine quantitatively in solu-

tion. This still remains a handicap to go beyond the concentration limit as recorded in the tables. In spite of this shortcoming, the tables show that in consideration of simplicity of operation, the procedure recommended by us will be convenient to microchemists.

We could not study the effect of interfering ions. It is self-evident that mercury and cadmium can always be estimated in presence of copper.

Indirect application of I^{131} , which is rather a popular isotope, is much more convenient in a radiochemical laboratory. In this work we have improved upon the method adopted by Spacu and have used I^{131} as a measuring indicator. Other co-ordination reagents may also be used for analytical purpose and an easier solution of the analytical problem may be attained by the use of radioactive nuclei.

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